

RARE DISEASES AND THE WHO MODEL LIST OF ESSENTIAL MEDICINES

Report of the RDI Working Group

REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Access to essential medicines is fundamental to achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and health equity, particularly for People Living With Rare Disease (PLWRD). Rare diseases (RDs) collectively affect over 300 million people worldwide, presenting unique challenges such as prolonged diagnostic journeys, limited treatment options, and high costs. Recognizing these challenges, Rare Diseases International (RDI) established the Essential Medicines Working Group (EMWG) in June 2024. This group aimed to enhance understanding of the World Health Organization Essential Medicines List (WHO EML) as a tool for improving access to medicines for RD. The EMWG has analyzed successful and unsuccessful applications to the EML, identified pitfalls and success factors in the application process, and advocated with a Call to Action.

The WHO EML is a globally recognized tool that identifies essential medicines based on efficacy, safety, cost-effectiveness, and public health relevance. Its purpose is to guide national procurement policies and improve access to life-saving treatments. While the inclusion of orphan drugs on the EML has increased over the years, and removal of the prevalence criteria, significant obstacles remain. These include high costs of RD treatments, lengthy timelines for inclusion after regulatory approval, and limited clinical evidence leading to application rejections.

The EMWG has utilized a structured methodology during its research, including stakeholder mapping, interviews with applicants, data analysis of past submissions, and development of case studies. Notable examples are included; these case studies highlight real-world challenges and successes in integrating RD medicines into healthcare systems.

In conclusion, while the WHO EML remains a fundamental tool for promoting global access to essential medicines, its impact on RD treatments requires further strengthening. By addressing existing barriers and advocating for systemic improvements, stakeholders can work together to advance health equity for PLWRD worldwide.

1. INTRODUCTION

Access to essential medicines is a pillar of Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and fundamental to achieving health equity, particularly for People Living With Rare Disease (PLWRD). While UHC aims to ensure that everyone has access to healthcare services, PLWRDs continue to face significant challenges. Rare diseases (RDs), though individually uncommon, collectively impact 3% to 8% of the global population—over 300 million people worldwide¹ RDs present unique challenges to healthcare systems worldwide, including difficulties in diagnosis, limited treatment options, high costs of available therapies, and a lack of awareness among healthcare professionals and the public². PLWRDs experience considerable unmet needs, including prolonged diagnostic journeys, limited treatment options, and a huge psychosocial burden due to the lack of coordinated, integrated care^{3,4}.

In recent years, rare diseases have gained greater visibility in the global health agenda. The 2019 United Nations (UN) Political Declaration on UHC explicitly included rare diseases, followed by the 2021 UN Resolution on Addressing the Challenges of Persons Living with a Rare Disease and their Families. These milestones underscore an increasing recognition of the need to strengthen health systems to meet the specific medical and care needs of PLWRD. Building on this momentum, Rare Diseases International (RDI) has launched a campaign for a World Health Assembly (WHA) Resolution on Rare Diseases with a Global Action Plan. During the 78th World Health Assembly in May 2025, the WHA Resolution “Rare diseases: a global health priority for equity and inclusion” was adopted.

The WHO, with its mandate to promote health for all, plays an important role in addressing the needs of PLWRD, and its Model List of Essential Medicines (EML) stands as a fundamental tool for promoting access to medicines globally. The EML, a global reference since 1977, has evolved to better address rare disease needs, especially since removing the prevalence-based criterion from the definition of “essential medicines” in 2000. This shift paved the way for greater inclusion of orphan drugs⁵.

As a part of its Programmes, RDI established the Essential Medicines Working Group (EMWG) in June 2024 to improve understanding of the WHO EML as a tool to enhance access to medicines for rare diseases. Composed of representatives from RDI member organizations and their members, the EMWG analyzed successful and unsuccessful applications for rare disease medicines to the EML, identifying challenges, success factors, and opportunity to strengthen the evaluation process for essential RD medicines. This report describes the results of the research carried out by the working group.

2. UNDERSTANDING THE WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION MODEL LIST OF ESSENTIAL MEDICINES

2.1 THE WHO MODEL LIST OF ESSENTIAL MEDICINES AND ITS RELEVANCE FOR RARE DISEASES

The WHO EML is a list of medications that the WHO considers essential for addressing the most important public health needs globally. These medicines are selected based on efficacy, safety, cost-effectiveness, and public health relevance. Since 1977, the WHO EML has been a benchmark to guide the procurement of medicines at the national level, especially in low and middle-income countries ^{6,7}. Ensuring both quality and affordability is central to EML's mission, guaranteeing that essential medicines are not only effective but also accessible to those who need them most. Its primary objective is to ensure that essential medicines are both effective and affordable, supporting improved health outcomes, cost reduction, and progress toward health equity and UHC ⁸.

Recognizing the specific healthcare needs of children, the WHO introduced the Essential Medicines List for Children (EMLc) in 2007. This specialized list identifies medicines and formulations appropriate for children up to 12 years of age.

Over time, the EML has evolved to better reflect the needs of people living with rare diseases (PLWRD). A pivotal change occurred in 2000, when the WHO removed the requirement that essential medicines must address conditions affecting the majority of the population. This shift allowed for the inclusion of treatments for rare diseases, provided they address priority healthcare needs. As a result, the proportion of EML-listed medicines with orphan indications approved by the FDA or EMA rose from 1.9% (4/208) in 1977 to 14.6% (70/478) in 2021 ⁵. This steady increase in the number of orphan drugs over the last two decades reflects growing alignment with global health priorities.

Nevertheless, significant challenges remain. The high costs of many orphan drugs pose accessibility and reimbursement challenges, especially in resource-limited settings. Moreover, the median time from regulatory approval (FDA, EMA) to EML inclusion is 13.5 years (range: 1–28 years), largely due to the WHO's requirement for rigorous evidence regarding the efficacy and safety of treatments ^{5,9}. Limited clinical evidence and uncertainty about treatment benefit are frequent reasons for rejection to add new orphan drugs to the EML.

Addressing the unmet needs of the rare disease community requires a multi-faceted approach. Continued efforts to improve the assessment and inclusion of effective and safe RDs drugs on the EML are crucial. Initiatives like the RDI EMWG are critical in advocating for more inclusive and responsive approaches to listing rare disease treatments on the WHO EML.

2.2 THE STRUCTURE OF THE WHO EML

The WHO EML is divided into two principal sections:

- The **Core List** comprises the essential medicines that represent the minimum requirements for a basic healthcare system. These medicines are selected for their proven efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness in treating priority health conditions. The designation of priority conditions is guided by current and anticipated public health relevance, along with the potential for safe and economically sound treatment.
- The **Complementary List** includes essential medicines intended for the management of priority diseases that require specialized diagnostic or monitoring tools, advanced medical care, or specific clinical expertise. Medicines may also be placed on the complementary list if their costs are consistently higher or if their cost-effectiveness is comparatively lower across diverse healthcare settings.

Additionally, certain medicines within the EML are denoted with a **square box symbol**, which signifies that there are therapeutic alternatives to the listed medicine ¹⁰. These alternatives, which may consist of individual medicines or groups within a pharmacological class or chemical subgroup (classified at the fourth level of the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system), are considered to have comparable clinical efficacy and safety. Such notation serves to guide national authorities in selecting the most appropriate medicine based on local health system capacities and needs.

2.3 VALUE AND GAPS OF THE EML FOR ACCESS

The WHO EML is a key tool for enhancing global access to medicines for a wide range of health conditions. **Inclusion in the WHO EML signifies that a medicine meets rigorous standards for efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness, and is recognized as part of the global standard of care.** This designation holds significant influence, guiding healthcare providers, informing patient advocacy, and shaping national health policies.

One significant feature of the WHO Model List is its dynamic nature, with regular updates reflecting the latest advancements in medical science and shifts in global health priorities. This fluidity is crucial to ensuring the EML remains a relevant and practical guide. The updating process allows for the incorporation of both innovative new treatments and older, well-established medicines, or cost-effectiveness alternatives. This consideration of affordability is particularly important for LMICs, where affordability remains a critical barrier to accessing essential medications.

Many countries rely on the EML to determine their National Medicine Lists (NML), which in turn guide procurement, reimbursement schemes, medicine donations, public sector supply, local production, and basis for national treatment guidelines ¹¹. Despite its benefits, the inclusion of medicine in the EML does not automatically guarantee availability or affordability

at the national level. Without addressing underlying systemic gaps, such as weak infrastructure, limited funding, or inadequate policy, EML listing alone may not translate into meaningful access for patients.

To achieve UHC, listing must be complemented by sustained government and stakeholder commitments, and investments to strengthen healthcare systems. Indeed, listing medicine is just the first aspect of improving access. An all-round approach is necessary to ensure that the inclusion of a medicine in the EML leads to tangible benefits for patients worldwide.

Case Study: Addressing Systemic Barriers to Rare Disease Medication Access in Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe struggles with access to life-saving medications for rare diseases, such as fludrocortisone for congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH). Fludrocortisone is listed in the WHO EML. For five years, Child Youth Care Zimbabwe (CYCZ), has worked to bridge this gap. CYCZ's experience underscores how systemic barriers – regulatory restrictions, high costs, and limited resources—can prevent vulnerable communities from accessing life-saving medication. Sustainable solutions require regulatory flexibility, advocacy, and strengthened local supply chains. This case study highlights how the adoption of EML in National Medicines List (NML) can support better access and sustainable solutions.

Saving Lives through Stable Supplies

- CYCZ initially partnered with a private pharmacy to import Fludrocortisone, covering costs for patients.
- A Pakistan supplier provided a stable, non-refrigerated supply for three years under a regulatory waiver, until a policy change in the country.
- During the three-year stable supply period, no child deaths occurred.

Regulatory Barriers

- After three years, the waiver for the importation of Fludrocortisone was not subsequently renewed due to a change in waiver requirements.
- The manufacturer did have the necessary compliance documents to enable the continuation of import.

Unsustainable access

- After regulatory barriers blocked alternatives, patients were left with expensive private out-of-pocket options.
- Reliance on private suppliers drove costs even higher, making the medication unaffordable for most families, as the medication expense consumed nearly 80% of their income.
- Importing refrigerated alternatives from South Africa is impractical for rural patients.

Gaps in the implementation of for EML

- Listing Fludrocortisone in the EML was achieved in 2009, thanks to additional partners, but this had no impact on Zimbabwe's National Medicines List
- Without the NML listing, local production is non-existent, and CYCZ empowered families to form a support group advocating for NML inclusion, but faced small patient numbers and stigma challenges so far

3. APPLICATION PROCESS FOR INCLUSION OF MEDICINES TO THE WHO EML

3.1 OVERSIGHT AND THE WHO EXPERT COMMITTEE

The WHO EML is an open resource that permits the submission of applications for the inclusion of new medicines. Any stakeholder can submit applications, including academic institutions, patient organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and pharmaceutical manufacturers. Organizations or individuals may submit applications with the objective of expanding global access to a specific therapeutic product. The EML is revised every two years to reflect changes in global health concerns, pharmaceutical developments, and patterns of drug resistance.

Oversight and management of the WHO EML are entrusted to two bodies: the **WHO EML Secretariat** and the **WHO Expert Committee on the Selection and Use of Essential Medicines**. The EML Secretariat, a technical unit within WHO, is responsible for coordinating and administering the EML update process. Its core functions include receiving and evaluating proposals for the addition, removal, or modification of medicines, facilitating the convening of the Expert Committee, ensuring a transparent and evidence-based selection process, and offering technical support to Member States in the implementation of the list at the national level. This systematic and rigorous framework ensures that the EML remains responsive to evolving global health priorities.

The Expert Committee is an independent panel of 18 specialists appointed by WHO. It is composed of global specialists from fields such as medicine, pharmacology, policy making, regulation, and health organizations. These experts assess submitted applications, reviewing the scientific evidence related to each medicine's efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness. Based on a thorough evaluation using well-defined criteria, the Committee formulates recommendations and updates the EML accordingly — adding new treatments that meet essential health needs and removing those deemed obsolete or less effective.

3.2 THE APPLICATION PROCESS

The application process for inclusion or revision of medicines on the EML involves submitting evidence-based proposals. It is a well-established, rigorous, transparent and evidence-based process (Figure 1). Requests for changes to the WHO EML (such as the addition of new medicines or formulations, removal of medicines or formulations, or expanding the listing of a medicine to include a new indication) are made through an open application process.

These submissions are reviewed by the WHO Expert Committee on Selection and Use of Essential Medicines, which evaluates factors such as public health relevance, efficacy,

safety, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility within healthcare systems. All applications received for consideration by the Expert Committee are published on the WHO website for public review and comment to ensure credibility and transparency. The resulting recommendations aim to ensure that essential medicines are always available in adequate amounts and appropriate forms within functioning health systems.

Case Study: EML Success Story with Leadership by a Patient Organization

The International Patient Organisation for Primary Immunodeficiencies (IPOPI) is a global association focused on improving awareness, diagnosis, and treatment for people with primary immunodeficiencies (PID). IPOPI successfully applied for the reintegration of Immunoglobulins (Igs) into the EML after their removal in 2003. In 2007, IPOPI resubmitted a strengthened application with a structured approach. This led to the reinstatement of Igs, starting with the intramuscular form. Subsequently, intravenous and subcutaneous forms were also added to the EML Complementary List. This case study also highlights the use of EML as advocacy tool for access at the national level.

Comprehensive Data Collection

- Gathered medical information and strong evidence.
- Collected data from different regions, providing evidence that the medicine submitted is relevant and beneficial on a global level.
- Provided essential information for the application from PID Centers.

Engage Global Experts and Community

- Collaborated with global experts.
- Engaged with **International Federations** and **National Organizations**.
- Leveraged **critical data sources**, such as PID Centers.
- Collected **support letters** to show a unified commitment of the community.

Positive Impact to Access at National Level

- **Bosnia:** a mother successfully advocated for her son's need for Igs by directly engaging the Ministry of Health.
- **Bolivia:** a new Ministry of Health regulation now mandates coverage regardless of age. In the past, patients over six years old faced out-of-pocket expenses for Igs, because they were no longer covered by the healthcare system.

Integrated Approach

After the medicine was listed in the EML, IPOPI submitted an application for the corresponding **diagnostic** device to be included in the Essential Diagnostics List (EDL), successfully creating an integrated approach that optimized the process and maximized benefits.

3.3 TIMELINE OF THE REVISIONS

The WHO periodically, every two years, updates the EML and the EMLc through a structured and transparent process. This ensures that these lists reflect the latest global healthcare needs. The revision process follows a series of key steps, each playing a crucial role in the evaluation and selection of medicines (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Key steps of the EML revision process

- 1. Opening of the Application Submission Period.** This first phase of the process begins with the public announcement of the opening of the application window, during which stakeholders can submit proposals for the addition, modification, or removal of a medicine from the EML and EMLc. This marks the start of the revision cycle.
- 2. Application Deadline.** Approximately eight months after the submission window opens, the application period closes. All received applications undergo a preliminary review to ensure they meet the eligibility criteria and include the required documentation. Applicants receive an official confirmation of their submission, ensuring traceability.

3. **Preliminary Quality Assessment.** Following submission, the applications are evaluated to determine eligibility for review by the Expert Committee. The outcome of this preliminary assessment is communicated through publication on the EML webpage of the accepted for evaluation applications.
4. **Public Commentary Period.** Following publication of the submission on the EML webpage, the WHO EML Secretariat invites interested stakeholders to read and submit relevant comments to the applications.
5. **Meeting of the Expert Committee on the Selection and Use of Essential Medicines.** The meeting is held at WHO Headquarters in Geneva, two or three months after the published applications for consideration. During this meeting, discussions and revisions of the lists take place.
6. **Publication of the Updated List.** Upon completing the review, the Expert Committee's decisions are formalized and integrated into the updated lists. The official publication of the revised EML and EMLc marks the conclusion of the revision cycle. The publication is typically scheduled for the summer period.

In conclusion, as global health challenges evolve, the continuous updating of the EML and EMLc will remain important for achieving UHC and improving health outcomes globally.

3.4 APPLICATION PREPARATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The EMWG identified recommendations and key lessons learnt through direct interviews of stakeholders who have applied to the EML.

The application preparation process for the WHO EML is notably extensive and burdensome for applicants. It demands significant time investment and dedicated human resources, as well as expertise.

A crucial aspect of this process is the identification of the “**optimal medicine**”, which involves assessing its feasibility across various global contexts, ensuring it meets specific medical needs, and evaluating its accessibility. This multifaceted process requires collaboration within the healthcare community. Engaging national organizations and international federations is essential to create synergy among patient advocacy groups, clinicians, and academic institutions. Such collaboration strengthens collective efforts and enhances the chances of a successful application. Additionally, gathering support letters from a diverse range of stakeholders can showcase the unified commitment of the community towards the proposed inclusion.

Having a structured methodology is beneficial in navigating this complex application process. Gathering as much evidence as possible is crucial; this includes providing up-to-date literature references, sufficient efficacy and safety data, and long-term evidence whenever possible. Comparative studies with the standard of care (SoC) are particularly important, as many applications have faced rejection due to insufficient supporting data. Applicants should also focus on collecting data and case examples from various regions of the world, especially including evidence from LMICs, to present a well-rounded perspective. This approach not only enhances the credibility of the application but also reflects a global understanding of the drug's impact and applicability. Furthermore, incorporating pricing data, such as cost and cost-effectiveness studies, along with health technology assessment (HTA) evaluations across different countries, can significantly strengthen the application. Demonstrating economic feasibility through these analyses is essential, as it provides a compelling argument for the drug's potential value in diverse healthcare settings. By addressing these factors comprehensively, applicants can improve their chances of successful approval.

To ensure compliance with WHO's requirements, applicants are strongly encouraged to familiarize themselves with the updated "Instructions for Applicants" guide and to engage with the EML Secretariat for guidance well before the submission deadline. The Secretariat is available to review applications and offer valuable advice and support before the application submission deadline.

4. CHALLENGES IN SUBMITTING APPLICATIONS FOR RARE DISEASE TREATMENTS

A number of challenges were consistently reported by stakeholders who have applied to the EML for rare disease treatments. They are drawn from real-world experiences shared through interviews conducted by the EMWG, providing a grounded understanding of the systemic barriers applicants face. Addressing these issues through improved expert support, more flexible evidence requirements, and tailored evaluation criteria is critical to ensuring that effective rare disease treatments are fairly assessed and made accessible worldwide.

4.1 LIMITATIONS IN EXPERTISE AND EVIDENCE EVALUATION FOR RARE DISEASES

The process of applying for inclusion in the WHO EML is rigorous and multifaceted, particularly for treatments addressing RDs. One of the primary challenges reported by stakeholders is the limited RD-specific expertise within the WHO Expert Committee. This gap can hinder the committee's ability to fully grasp the nuances of rare disease conditions, such as small and heterogeneous patient populations, atypical disease progression, and the complexity of underlying mechanisms.

Compounding this challenge is the difficulty of meeting conventional evidence standards. It is critical that the EML evaluation process distinguishes between traditional evidence standards with the broader clinical and societal value of RD treatments. Even when the data is limited, these medicines may address significant unmet needs of underserved patient groups. Weighing potential impact against limited data is essential for a context-sensitive approach to evaluate rare diseases treatments.

4.2 LIMITED DATA FOR RARE DISEASES

Evidence generation is another major obstacle. RDs frequently lack robust clinical evidence due to small patient populations, which makes conducting large-scale, randomized controlled trials difficult. Available data is often derived from small, uncontrolled, or observational studies, with long-term outcomes frequently lacking—particularly for conditions with high infant mortality. As a result, data limitations about safety, efficacy, and overall benefit often lead to application rejections.

Economic and cost data availability also pose barriers for broader considerations as essential medicines. Applicants must demonstrate evidence of cost-effectiveness of the medicine through health technology assessment (HTA), and comparisons to the standard-of-care. However, conducting these evaluations can be resource-intensive and complicated by the lack of alternative treatment options or comparative data.

4.3 CONSTRAINTS FROM THE EML FRAMEWORK

The EML traditionally emphasizes treatment rather than prevention. For example, evaluating preventive products such as sunscreen requires specific ingredients analysis, a process that is not always straightforward or aligned with current EML methodologies. This can lead to difficulties in evaluating product classes that do not fit neatly into the existing framework.

Similarly, the global inconsistency in diagnostic capacity can limit the practical applicability of certain treatments in low-resource settings. For instance, some therapies require advanced biomarker testing or specialized healthcare infrastructure that may not be widely accessible. This lack of diagnostic infrastructure can hinder both the assessment of a medicine’s feasibility for inclusion and its real-world applicability. Treatments that depend on specialist services or advanced diagnostics are typically listed on the EML Complementary List, which assumes the availability of more complex healthcare infrastructure. However, for many rare diseases, such specialist care is limited or absent.

Finally, the application process itself can be lengthy and resource intensive. Applicants have to provide comprehensive data on clinical benefits, safety, cost-effectiveness, and infrastructure requirements; an effort that can be discouraging for smaller organizations.

Phases	Recommendations
Before Application window opens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start planning in advance. • Identify the <i>optimal</i> medicine: its appropriateness for specific medical needs and accessibility across different global contexts.
Application Preparation Process	<p>Project management and approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest time and dedicated human resources. • Use a structured methodology. • Follow the updated "Instructions for Applicants" provided by the WHO. • Have the dossier reviewed by the EML Secretariat for valuable feedback to improve the application. <p>Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather as much evidence as possible: provide up-to-date literature references, efficacy and safety data, and long-term evidence (when possible). • Include comparative studies with the Standard-of-Care or other treatments. • Incorporate pricing data: cost, cost-effectiveness studies, Health Technology Assessment (HTA) evaluations across different countries. • For all data requirements, provide evidence from multiple regions of the world, including LMICs <p>Community synergy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create collaboration among the stakeholder groups to support comprehensive data collection. • Engage with International Federations and National Organizations. • Collaborate with Clinicians, Academic Institutions and other stakeholders. • Gather support letters from a diverse range of stakeholders to showcase the overall support towards the proposed application. <p>Key objective</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is important to demonstrate the value of the application in a global context.
Post Submission period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue to gather support letters from a diverse range of stakeholders to showcase the collective strength and commitment around the application.

Table 1: Recommendations and ways to strengthen EML applications

5. CALL-TO-ACTION: OPTIMIZING WHO MODEL LIST OF ESSENTIAL MEDICINES FOR RARE DISEASE IMPACT

The WHO EML serves as a cornerstone for global access to therapies, yet its impact on rare disease requires targeted enhancements. This Call-to-Action outlines the following recommendations to improving EML strategic use and innovating regulatory processes.

1. **Revisit the EML assessment framework for RD medicines** to address challenges related to evidence generation and cost-effectiveness. Consider, as an option, adopting a conditional approval pathway, similar to those used by EMA and FDA for orphan drugs, where preliminary approval is granted based on limited initial data. Applicants would then be required to submit additional evidence over time to confirm therapeutic benefits, ensuring treatments meet safety and efficacy standards while balancing timely patient access with robust evidence generation.
2. **Establishment of a EML Rare Diseases Working Group**, to support and recommend RD medicines to the WHO Expert Committee. The aim is to create a dedicated working group similar to the EML Cancer Medicines Working Group (CMWG), which provides independent evaluation and expert advice on the selection of optimal cancer medicines for potential inclusion in the WHO EML.
3. **Enhance the visibility of rare diseases** by encouraging the WHO to take **practical actions**, such as integrating searchable filters or tags into the electronic EML platform to facilitate searches for RD medicines.
4. **Encourage WHO to strengthen support for Member States in implementing measures for the use of the EML**, transforming it from a document into an operational tool. This requires commitment from the global level down to local communities, including more frequent monitoring of the effective implementation of the EML to NML worldwide.
5. **Bridge the gap between including a medicine on the EML and ensuring its access & reimbursement nationwide**. Engaging with national regulatory agencies and procurement agencies to raise awareness and explore how these entities could play a role in improving access at national level.
6. Build synergies and activities as a part of the **Global Action Plan** of the pending **WHA Resolution for Rare Diseases**.

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ANNEX: METHODOLOGY OF THE RDI ESSENTIAL MEDICINES WORKING GROUP

ESTABLISHMENT AND OBJECTIVES OF THE WORKING GROUP

In 2024 RDI initiated a working group with the aim to facilitate the understanding of EML as a tool to improve access to medicines and enhance how rare disease medicines are assessed by the WHO Expert Committee on the Selection and Use of Essential Medicines. On the 4th of April 2024 RDI organized a webinar for its members with WHO EML Secretariat to explain the EML and the implication for rare diseases, as a capacity building activity. In the following months, an open call for expression of interest has been launched for RDI members and its members.

The RDI Essential Medicines Working Group was launched officially on June 2024 and comprised of RDI Secretariat and 12 representatives both national and international federations across all regions. Online meetings were scheduled approximately every two months to facilitate discussion and actions; during these meetings, the work has been carried forward and activity updates have been presented.

OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK OF THE WORKING GROUP

The Working Group (WG) adopted a structured, multi-phase approach to capture stakeholder experiences and inform improvements in the application process for the WHO Essential Medicines List (EML) as it pertains to rare diseases.

Development of Interview Guide - The first activity undertaken was the development of a semi-structured interview guide. This tool was specifically designed to systematically document stakeholder experiences and generate informative case studies. The guide supported the “Mapping Experience” phase, during which interviews with diverse global health stakeholders were conducted to gather first-hand insights related to the EML.

Stakeholder Mapping and Interviewee Selection - The EMWG then compiled a list of potential stakeholders who had previously applied to or engaged with the EML in the context of rare diseases. Sources included the electronic EML database and existing community networks. Concurrently, an analysis of the rare disease medicines listed in the EML was carried out, allowing identification of the corresponding applicants. An initial pool of 40 stakeholders was identified, spanning patient organizations, academic institutions, non-profit organizations (NPOs), statutory bodies, and pharmaceutical companies. A set of organizations were prioritized for interviews. These interviews were distributed and carried out among EMWG members. Ultimately, 19 interviews were completed. The stakeholder composition was as follows:

- Patient Organizations: 6
- Academia: 5

- Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs): 4
- Pharmaceutical Companies: 3
- Statutory Body: 1

Data Analysis - Using the interview guide, the WG captured detailed accounts of stakeholders' interactions with the EML. Each interview was individually reviewed and analyzed to ensure depth and accuracy. From this analysis, three overarching thematic areas were identified:

1. Application Process
2. Challenges
3. Impact and Value of the EML

These findings were compiled into an "Analysis Table" to systematically categorize the insights and facilitate comparative analysis across interviews.

Communication and Knowledge Translation - To broaden community understanding of the EML, an educational fact sheet was developed. This document outlines the purpose and structure of the EML and provides illustrative examples. To reach a global audience, the fact sheet was translated into English, Spanish, French, and Portuguese. Recognizing the EML's potential to improve equitable access to medicines for people living with rare diseases, this initiative aimed to enhance its visibility and utility across diverse contexts.

A second fact sheet focusing specifically on the EML application process was also published. This resource incorporates summaries of the actionable recommendations to further support stakeholders in preparing successful applications.

Resources

PUBLIC WEBINAR “ Leveraging the EML for Access to Rare Disease Treatments”

- [English](#)
- [Spanish](#)

FACT SHEET: WHO Essential Medicine List: Opportunities for Rare Diseases

- [English](#)
- [Spanish](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [French](#)